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**Leadership behavior and its impact on the work motivation of managerial
personnel**

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Abstract: The article examines the impact of leadership behavior on the work motivation of managerial personnel under conditions of socio-economic instability and martial law in Ukraine. The purpose of the study is to systematize contemporary scientific approaches to understanding the relationship between leadership style and the level of intrinsic motivation among managers, as well as to identify effective management strategies that ensure productivity and psychological resilience of teams during periods of crisis-induced change. The methodological framework of the research includes comparative, systemic, and analytical methods, which made it possible to generalize theoretical concepts of leadership (transformational, servant, and humble leadership) and to reveal the specifics of their implementation in modern Ukrainian organizations. A contextual analysis approach was applied, allowing the integration of international research findings with domestic experience in personnel management during wartime.

The study found that transformational leadership contributes to the formation of a shared vision, increased employee engagement, and the development of intrinsic motivation by satisfying basic psychological needs – autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Servant leadership was identified as an effective mechanism for strengthening trust and psychological safety, which are key factors in maintaining productivity under crisis conditions. Humble leadership, based on modesty, reflection,

and open communication, promotes initiative, creativity, and emotional resilience within managerial teams. It was proven that Ukrainian leadership experience is characterized by the integration of humanistic and crisis-oriented approaches focused on maintaining team morale and ensuring effective management amid persistent risks.

The results confirm that effective leadership behavior directly influences the level of intrinsic motivation of managerial personnel by mediating this effect through the creation of an atmosphere of trust, support, and open dialogue. It was found that combining different leadership styles is a prerequisite for adaptive management during crises, while the development of leaders' emotional intelligence enhances their ability to reduce employee anxiety and prevent burnout. The Ukrainian experience demonstrates that a leader's moral and ethical responsibility, transparency in decision-making, and support for socially significant initiatives form a unique model of management grounded in mutual trust, empathy, and value orientation.

The conclusions emphasize that leadership behavior is a determining factor in managerial motivation, ensuring engagement, resilience, and readiness to act under uncertainty. It is recommended to implement a comprehensive approach to leadership development focused on combining transformational and servant leadership principles, strengthening emotional intelligence, and cultivating a corporate culture of trust. The results obtained can be applied to improve personnel management practices in Ukrainian organizations during wartime and post-war transformations.

Keywords: leadership, motivation, managerial work, management style, human resource management.

**Лідерська поведінка та її вплив на мотивацію праці управлінського
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Анотація: У статті досліджено вплив лідерської поведінки на мотивацію праці управлінського персоналу в умовах соціально-економічної нестабільності та воєнного стану в Україні. Мета роботи полягає у систематизації сучасних наукових підходів до розуміння взаємозв'язку між стилем лідерства та рівнем внутрішньої мотивації управлінців, а також у визначенні ефективних стратегій управління, що забезпечують продуктивність і психологічну стійкість команд в умовах кризових змін. Методологічну основу дослідження становлять порівняльний, системний та аналітичний методи, які дозволили узагальнити теоретичні концепції лідерства (трансформаційного, сервант- та humble leadership), а також виявити специфіку їх реалізації у сучасних українських організаціях. Застосовано підхід контекстного аналізу, що дало змогу інтегрувати результати міжнародних досліджень із вітчизняним досвідом управління персоналом у період війни.

У результаті дослідження встановлено, що трансформаційне лідерство сприяє формуванню спільного бачення, підвищенню залученості персоналу та розвитку внутрішньої мотивації через задоволення базових психологічних потреб – автономії, компетентності та взаємозв'язку. Сервант-лідерство виявлено як ефективний механізм зміцнення довіри та психологічної безпеки працівників, що є ключовим чинником підтримання продуктивності у кризових умовах. Humble leadership, засноване на скромності, рефлексії та відкритій комунікації, сприяє розвитку ініціативності, креативності та емоційної стійкості управлінських команд. Доведено, що український досвід лідерства вирізняється інтеграцією гуманістичних і антикризових підходів, орієнтованих на збереження морального духу колективів та ефективне управління в умовах постійних ризиків.

Отримані результати підтверджують, що ефективна лідерська поведінка безпосередньо впливає на рівень внутрішньої мотивації управлінського персоналу, опосередковуючи цей вплив через створення атмосфери довіри, підтримки та відкритого діалогу. Виявлено, що поєднання різних стилів

лідерства є необхідною умовою гнучкого управління під час криз, а розвиток емоційного інтелекту керівників посилює їхню здатність знижувати рівень тривожності працівників і запобігати вигоранню. Український досвід доводить, що морально-етична відповідальність лідера, прозорість управлінських рішень і підтримка соціально значущих ініціатив формують унікальну модель управління, що базується на взаємній довірі, емпатії та ціннісній орієнтації.

У висновках підкреслено, що лідерська поведінка виступає визначальним чинником мотивації праці управлінців, забезпечуючи їхню залученість, стійкість і готовність діяти в умовах невизначеності. Рекомендовано впроваджувати комплексний підхід до розвитку лідерства, орієнтований на поєднання трансформаційних і сервант-принципів, розвиток емоційного інтелекту та формування корпоративної культури довіри. Отримані результати можуть бути використані для удосконалення практик управління персоналом у вітчизняних організаціях у період воєнних і післявоєнних трансформацій.

Ключові слова: лідерство, мотивація, праця менеджера, стиль управління, управління персоналом.

Problem Statement. In the current conditions of global instability, economic transformations, and social challenges, the issue of effective leadership has acquired particular significance. In Ukraine, where society and organizations operate under the complex circumstances of martial law, the role of leadership behavior in maintaining motivation, cohesion, and psychological resilience of managerial teams becomes critically important. The ability of teams to adapt to changes, maintain productivity, and stay focused on common goals despite external difficulties largely depends on leaders. In this context, studying the impact of leadership behavior on the motivation of managerial personnel is not only scientifically relevant but also practically necessary to ensure the sustainable development of organizations of various types, ranging from business structures to governmental institutions.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. The issue of managerial personnel motivation remains central in contemporary management studies. Classical theories, such as Herzberg's two-factor theory and Adams' equity theory, laid the foundations for understanding what drives employee motivation. Modern researchers, including Zh. Kudaybergenov, A. Dosbenbetova, A. Kurmanalina, and B. Bolatov, have reinterpreted Herzberg's propositions in the context of contemporary management, demonstrating that both hygiene and motivational factors remain key elements in shaping career development for managers [1]. They emphasize that hygiene factors, such as stability, safe working conditions, and fairness in rewards, create a baseline for satisfaction, whereas motivational factors – recognition, professional growth, and opportunities for self-actualization – enhance engagement and intrinsic motivation. This approach reflects the contemporary view of managerial motivation as a multidimensional process requiring consideration of both material and psychological aspects of incentivization. Meanwhile, Adams' equity theory highlights that perceived fairness in reward distribution significantly affects employee behavior, an important consideration for managers designing incentive systems.

Contemporary studies build upon these classical approaches by focusing on internal psychological mechanisms of motivation. For instance, Ryan R. M. and Deci E. L., within the framework of Self-Determination Theory, identify three basic psychological needs – autonomy, competence, and relatedness – whose fulfillment fosters sustained intrinsic motivation [2]. Their concept has formed the basis for many modern personnel management models, where the leader is viewed not only as a source of influence but also as a driver of the team's motivational potential.

Recent research increasingly emphasizes the link between leadership behavior and employees' intrinsic motivation. Transformational leadership, in particular, is considered one of the most effective styles for enhancing employee engagement and readiness for change. Gunawan, C., and Bangun, W. demonstrated that transformational leadership positively influences job satisfaction, acting as a catalyst for innovation and emotional involvement of employees [3]. Similar results were

reported in a study published in the *Future Business Journal*, showing that transformational leaders reduce professional burnout and social loafing while increasing productivity through strengthening intrinsic motivation [4].

Xu, G., Zeng, J., Wang, H., Qian, C., and Gu, X. found that the effect of leadership on employee motivation is mediated by the creation of psychological safety, where employees feel free to express ideas and take initiative [5]. Likewise, Junbish, R. K., Nayel, A. N., and Zadran, H. G. showed that intrinsic motivation mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative employee behavior [6]. These findings underscore that modern management cannot rely solely on control or material incentives; the development of trust, support, and a sense of shared purpose becomes a key factor.

Special attention is given to the concept of humble leadership, which emphasizes leaders' modesty and self-reflection. It is seen as a counterbalance to authoritarian management models dominant in previous decades. Hasanein, A. M., and Ayad, T. H. demonstrated that humble leadership positively affects employee performance by enhancing psychological safety [7]. Similarly, Tao R. found that humble leadership fosters employee creativity, particularly in teams with high levels of trust [8].

Alongside the development of Western leadership approaches, Ukrainian researchers focus on the practical dimension of the problem, taking into account the context of war and socio-economic instability. Nastenکو, M., Yokhna, M., Kryvoruchko, O., Savitskaya, M., and Ivanenko, V. showed that implementing servant leadership in the service sector positively impacts motivation and employee retention, particularly under conditions of uncertainty and psychological stress [9]. The domestic context necessitates combining humanistic leadership approaches with crisis-oriented management models, prioritizing trust, mutual support, and the ethical responsibility of leaders toward their teams.

The relevance of these studies is further confirmed by recent publications, including Jameel, A., Guo, W., Hussain, A., et al., who demonstrated that transformational leadership, by fostering intrinsic motivation and employee creativity,

promotes innovative behavior, especially in the hospitality industry, which is highly sensitive to crises. These results align with findings that a leader's motivational effectiveness directly depends on their ability to create a psychologically safe environment where employees can realize their potential and feel engaged in shared goals [10].

Overall, the analysis of scientific sources illustrates an evolution in understanding the relationship between leadership behavior and motivation: from external stimuli and control to internal factors of self-development, participation, and psychological resilience. In the current context of war in Ukraine, this issue gains particular importance, as effective leadership serves not only as a tool for enhancing productivity but also as a mechanism for maintaining morale, cohesion, and professional endurance of managerial teams.

Identification of Unresolved Aspects of the Overall Problem. Despite numerous studies on the relationship between leadership behavior and employee motivation, several issues remain insufficiently explored, particularly in contexts of rapid change and crisis, such as those observed in Ukraine during wartime. First, a more detailed analysis is required of how different leadership styles – transformational, servant, and humble leadership – influence the intrinsic motivation of managerial personnel under conditions of high psychological stress and uncertainty. Second, it is necessary to investigate the mechanisms of indirect influence of leadership behavior through psychological safety, trust, and a sense of shared purpose on team productivity and creativity. Third, there is a need for a comparative analysis of domestic and international experiences, which would help identify adapted motivation and leadership strategies capable of ensuring not only work efficiency but also the psychological resilience of managerial teams in crisis situations. Therefore, further research should integrate psychological, organizational, and social aspects of leadership to develop practical recommendations for managers who can maintain both productivity and staff morale even under conditions of war and instability.

Formulation of the Article's Objectives (Statement of the Task). The aim of the study is to systematize contemporary scientific approaches to examining the influence of leadership on managerial motivation and to identify effective strategies that ensure both productivity and psychological resilience of teams in conditions of dynamic change. To achieve this aim, the article outlines a series of interconnected tasks aimed at a comprehensive investigation of the phenomenon of leadership behavior and its impact on the motivation of managerial personnel. In particular, it is necessary to analyze key theories of motivation and leadership within the context of managerial activity, which will allow the identification of theoretical foundations for the relationship between leadership style and employee engagement levels. It is also important to examine the transformation of management practices in modern organizations, taking into account the challenges of globalization, digitalization, socio-economic changes, as well as wartime conditions that impose new requirements for management effectiveness. Special attention is given to identifying the mechanisms through which leadership behavior influences intrinsic motivation, as internal factors – such as the need for self-realization, recognition, and professional development – play a crucial role in ensuring effective managerial performance. For a deeper understanding of the problem, the study includes an analysis and synthesis of both domestic and international leadership experiences, which will make it possible to identify common trends and national peculiarities in managerial approaches. Based on the results obtained, practical recommendations will be formulated for managers, aimed at enhancing the motivation of managerial personnel and developing effective leadership behavior in Ukrainian organizations during periods of wartime and post-war transformations.

Presentation of the Main Research Material. In the contemporary business environment, Ukrainian organizations face unprecedented challenges that have fundamentally transformed their operational and managerial realities. Traditional hierarchical structures and rigid control mechanisms, which previously ensured order and predictability, have proven ineffective during crises. Uncertainty, high dynamism,

and limited resources demand rapid response, flexibility, and a high level of autonomy from managerial personnel. In this context, the role of a leader has evolved from a mere manager to a moral and psychological guide, capable of maintaining team resilience, providing support in difficult situations, and fostering long-term employee motivation [11]. Research confirms that leaders who employ adaptive leadership – demonstrating empathy and the ability to make prompt decisions – are the most effective. Adaptive leadership involves the leader’s capacity to adjust their management style according to situational demands: adopting an authoritarian approach in critical conditions, a democratic style to stimulate initiative, or delegating authority where it enhances team efficiency and accountability [12].

A key aspect requiring detailed consideration is the unique combination of different leadership styles in Ukrainian managerial practice. Transformational leadership remains foundational, as it enables the creation of a shared vision of the future despite destructive realities. Managers inspire their teams by showing that work holds not only economic but also societal value, helping employees overcome existential challenges. For example, in the IT sector, leaders actively support volunteer projects, allocate resources for community initiatives, and organize educational and charitable programs. In the manufacturing sector, they reorient production toward defense needs, produce essential equipment for the frontlines, and supply critical goods [13]. Such practices create a sense of purpose and meaningful work, serving as a powerful intrinsic motivator and fostering employees’ sense of personal value and social significance.

Simultaneously, servant leadership has gained critical importance. Leaders focusing on employees’ physical and psychological safety earn deep trust. Providing assistance with relocation, ensuring shelters, organizing psychological counseling, and coordinating medical and social support have become daily practices that strengthen the connection between leadership and the team [15]. This aligns with the fundamental need for safety, which, according to Maslow’s hierarchy, is essential under extreme conditions.

Supportive leadership in Ukrainian companies emphasizes the emotional component of management. Leaders who regularly engage with employees, inquire about their physical and mental well-being, create an atmosphere of psychological safety, and allow open expression of fears and concerns reduce burnout and anxiety, foster psychological comfort, and enhance intrinsic motivation. The significance of humble leadership has also increased. Managers who acknowledge their own shortcomings and seek advice from subordinates break down hierarchical barriers and stimulate initiative, fostering collective responsibility, employee participation in decision-making, and active involvement in organizational development [2].

Communication during crises becomes one of the most crucial leadership tools. Transparent and honest sharing of information regarding organizational status, financial stability, strategic plans, and current challenges significantly reduces uncertainty and anxiety among staff. Leaders who provide timely information, even when not positive, build trust and reinforce a sense of stability. Effective delegation to lower management levels allows for rapid response to changes, increases productivity, and simultaneously satisfies basic needs for autonomy and competence, consistent with Self-Determination Theory [2].

Comparisons of Ukrainian experience with international practices reveal significant differences. In stable countries, leaders often adhere to formal procedures and regulations and lean toward transactional leadership based on rewards [16]. In Ukraine, war has compelled managers to exhibit exceptional flexibility, responsiveness, and emotional openness. Leaders combine strategic thinking with psychological support and team collaboration, ensuring organizational resilience in extremely challenging conditions. Managers experiencing traumatic events must possess self-regulation and emotional management skills to maintain team psychological safety. Leaders who openly acknowledge emotional challenges and seek support set an example, reducing the stigma associated with mental health issues.

Emotional intelligence is a key managerial tool. It enables leaders not only to understand their own emotions but also to effectively manage the team's emotional

state. In war conditions, where employees face constant stress, a leader's ability to demonstrate empathy, provide support, and remain a pillar of stability is critically important. Implementing stress-management and psychological support programs for managers is necessary, as they often experience dual pressures, serving as intermediaries between senior leadership and staff [17]. Organizational flexibility and effective remote management, including the transition to hybrid work models, required leaders to acquire new skills in communication, motivation, and maintaining team spirit remotely. This positively affected employee autonomy and competence, optimized processes, and preserved productivity despite limited office access.

War has also transformed HR practices in Ukrainian companies. The focus has shifted from aggressive talent acquisition to retention and development of existing personnel. Motivation systems have been revised: financial bonuses, flexible schedules, remote work opportunities, psychological counseling, and relocation support have become standard corporate policies. This demonstrates leaders' awareness of new employee needs under existential threats and highlights organizational adaptability to external changes.

Ethical leadership, grounded in fairness, honesty, and transparency, is a key factor in shaping positive corporate culture and strengthening trust [18]. Leaders who declare and embody values aligned with societal demands – for instance, supporting the Armed Forces of Ukraine or volunteer initiatives – enhance the meaningfulness of each team member's work, reinforcing the connection between employees and the organization's mission.

Leaders act as agents of resilience, helping teams develop adaptive skills and recover quickly from setbacks. Research shows that psychologically resilient managers effectively transfer this resilience to their teams, serving as mentors who guide staff through difficulties [18]. Regular feedback sessions and stress-management tools prevent burnout, increase intrinsic motivation, and improve organizational performance.

Managing personnel during wartime becomes an art of balancing emotional support with rational decision-making. Leaders who show empathy while making difficult management decisions ensure team stability and psychological safety. This creates a unique organizational culture where mutual assistance, resilience, and shared responsibility become core values. Employees become partners rather than mere executors, increasing autonomy and initiative, fostering new solutions, and advancing organizational development.

Such an approach not only motivates existing personnel but also makes organizations more attractive to talented individuals seeking a safe and meaningful work environment. When human capital is a key resource, organizations prioritizing employee well-being gain a competitive advantage. Employees recognize that their work supports not only their families but also the country's economic front. This transformational aspect of leadership offers a unique lesson for global practice, demonstrating that effective management relies on a combination of emotional intelligence, resilience, and ethical responsibility.

The Ukrainian experience illustrates that true leadership lies not only in making correct decisions but also in preserving humanity under the most difficult circumstances, ensuring organizational survival and growth. This combination of psychological support, resilience, strategic thinking, and ethical standards forms effective managerial practice capable of withstanding any crisis and serving as a model for international management.

Conclusions. The analysis of contemporary scientific sources and the unique Ukrainian experience allows several key conclusions to be drawn. First, leadership behavior is a decisive factor in shaping the intrinsic motivation and productivity of managerial personnel under crisis conditions. Second, the Ukrainian experience demonstrates the high effectiveness of integrated leadership, which synergistically combines transformational, servant, and supportive styles. This approach enables the maintenance of high productivity and psychological resilience. Third, effective communication, delegation of authority, and the development of emotional intelligence

are critically important tools for reducing uncertainty and enhancing employee engagement. The distinctiveness of the Ukrainian experience lies in the exceptional flexibility and moral-ethical responsibility of leaders, offering valuable lessons for global management theory.

Therefore, it is recommended that managers adopt a comprehensive approach to leadership, situationally integrating various styles. Special attention should be given to providing psychological support for personnel and implementing stress-management programs. Leaders should ensure transparent communication and actively involve subordinates in decision-making. Demonstrating empathy, acknowledging personal limitations, and supporting initiative are key to fostering an atmosphere of trust. Overall, the Ukrainian experience confirms that effective leadership is a cornerstone of organizational resilience and prosperity, even under the most challenging conditions.

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